

Sustain Sahel

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I. Executive summary

SustainSahel's dissemination approach is now at its second year of implementation, and the open field days are one of its key elements. From the planning phase, the open field days created concrete synergies between the project partners, WPs and disciplines, thus kickstarting the transdisciplinary collaboration within the project frame on the ground and acting as a platform for mutual learning. Despite initial delays due to changes in the project's consortium, the project partners took the dissemination approach in their hands and the first open field days were organized in six project sites in the second quarter of 2022. By now, 19 open field days have been organized in six project sites, to which 9 additional events by the project's dissemination expansion sister project – DAAPS – can be added. The relatively early start of the dissemination approach in the timeline of the project is already yielding its fruits, with a consolidated collaboration between farmers, researchers, farmers' organizations, students and extension officers that facilitates the flow of information and the openness to each other's perspectives and messages. The open field days are integrated into a systemic approach, where links to the Innovation Platforms (IP) and to the newly created internal sharing forum contribute to deepening the discussions on the proposed CSL practices and the pathway to their adoption. SustainSahel partners had the opportunity to attend a four-week comprehensive online training organized in 12 different modules, covering all aspects and steps regarding the farmer field school approach. This was a significant additional activity and external funding originally not foreseen in the DoA brought to the project. The current deliverable highlights the connections between the open field days and other elements of the project's dissemination approach, providing insights into what has already been achieved, as well as an update on the latest decisions and the vision concerning the upcoming phases.

2. SustainSahel's dissemination approach – an update

2.1 Background, achievements and challenges of the open field days

The project's dissemination strategy has been jointly drafted by all of the project members towards the end of 2021. The collective drafting of this strategy was a significant step in redirecting WP8's process in the right direction, after the withdrawal of the former work package's leadership in that year¹. The document has been shared in Annex B of deliverable D8.1, and outlined an action plan to coordinate the main steps and distribution of responsibilities in the dissemination process. One of the unusual but key features of this dissemination strategy is the early start in the project's timeline, allowing to build up a trust relationship between the project members, farmers and other stakeholders involved in the process. An early start has also provided a more solid ground to co-create the agendas, content and learning materials for the open field days, as outlined below.

¹ The project partner MINERVA (UK) officially withdrew from the consortium in 2022 due to difficulties in implementing and managing dissemination activities at local level. FiBL stepped in to fill the gap, given the institute could provide the necessary capacity for this role.

Main goals

The dissemination strategy is embedded in the overarching objectives of the project, which seeks to enhance the resilience of farming systems in the Sahel through the study and dissemination of appropriate crop-shrub/tree-livestock management practices. The main goals of this strategy can be summarized as follows:

1. To disseminate appropriate crop-shrub/tree-livestock management practices in six of the project sites: Ouarkhokh, Niakhar (Senegal); Koulikoro, Sikasso (Mali); Saria, Yilou (Burkina Faso);
2. To integrate relevant existing knowledge with new one emanating from the project's results, in a spirit of transdisciplinary collaboration between all project partners;
3. To work closely with other work packages in order to maximize the synergies between different activities, such as the study of the socio-economic impact of the disseminated practices (particularly with WP3); the innovation platforms' discussions (coordinated by WP2), which can greatly benefit from the inputs and interlinkages with the dissemination process; and the new project mechanism, SustainSahel's internal sharing forum (jointly coordinated by WP8 and WP2);
4. To empower smallholder farmers to become the owners and disseminators of the practices themselves, in all of the project sites. This applies firstly to the lead farmers, who are directly engaged with the project in a continuous way between 2022 and 2025. Eventually, more farmers are expected to join and own the process as the project unfolds.

Achievements and relevance

The dissemination strategy provided a unique opportunity for project partners to work closely together in the co-organization of the events and the definition of the agenda and the content to be disseminated. In practice, this resulted in the launch of the transdisciplinary approach that the project aims at, providing a tangible platform for farmers' organizations, researchers of different disciplines, and innovation platform members (many of whom are farmers) to collectively brainstorm about the key messages and the format of the open field days. This process of co-creation is a learning process and most local teams needed some time to overcome obstacles such as language barriers and stereotypical notions that underline (and undermine) the habitually fragmented relationships between the different disciplines and between academic and non-academic partners. One of the greatest achievements that the process generated, and which was lively expressed during the project's annual meeting in February 2023 in Burkina Faso, is that the boundaries between different types of participants have started to dissolve and active collaboration emerged after a few co-organized open field days. Another common remark during the workshop dedicated to the dissemination strategy during the annual meeting, was that starting a dissemination process early in the lifetime of the project has numerous advantages, not only because of the time needed to fine-tune the collaborative transdisciplinary approach among project partners but also to build trust relationships with the farmers and their communities, thus facilitating the co-learning and acceptance of the project's messages.

The guidelines outlined by the dissemination strategy provided a working framework for the local teams, easing the organization of the open field day events and harmonizing the approach in the three countries so that the dynamics of innovation trial, adoption, and ownership by farmers could be better understood by the end of the project. The harmonized approach means that 1) the different local teams use a similar agenda for the open field day events, 2) the number of events organized in each site is the same, and 3) the follow-up of the lead farmers is done similarly in the different sites. Despite a harmonized approach

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in the three countries, the open field day events naturally reflect the rich cultural and ecological diversity in the project sites, as well as the differences between the local teams and the co-selected set of innovations to be tested.

According to the local dissemination action plan document, the local teams should organize two open field day events per year. The first event should take place before the rainy season, so that farmers get familiar with the concepts and practices concerning the disseminated innovations, and the second one by the end of the season, when crops are mature and the effects of the different treatments can be visually assessed.

The local teams successfully organized the two annual events of 2022 and the first ones of 2023, in a total of 18 open field day events organized by the farmers' organizations in six project sites. In Koulikoro, an extra dissemination event took place in October 2022, organized by the research partner IPR, which consisted in an open field day for farmers in the research station of Katibougou. The dates and attendance figures of the 19 open field day events can be seen in table I.

Table I. Dates and attendance of the 19 open field day events organized by June 2023 in the six project sites.

Country	Site	Date	Lead Farmers	Total Participants*
Senegal	Niakhar	21/06/2022	14	24
		23/09/2022	23	29
		27/04/2023	38	65
	Ouarkhokh	23/06/2022	15	35
		21/09/2022	15	38
		25/04/2023	8	48
Mali	Koulikoro	11/06/2022	29	77
		24/10/2022	29	97
		19/10/2022	30	167
		29/05/2023	24	74
	Sikasso	04/06/2022	30	74
		31/10/2022	22	72
		02/06/2023	29	96
Burkina Faso	Saria	31/05/2022	40	70
		26/09/2022	40	90
		12/05/2023	30	62
	Yilou	30/05/2022	40	70
		03/11/2022	40	80
		09/05/2023	33	65

*The number of total participants includes other farmers (e.g. Innovation platform's members, other farmers from the village), representatives of the farmers' organization, research institution and extension structures.

Capacity development

The coordinating team of SustainSahel and particularly of WP8 and WP2 have been investing in the capacity development of local partners in the organization of the open field days. Regular meetings have been organized, in order to foster the co-learning and promote the transdisciplinary approach in the process.

Besides the online and in-person meetings with the farmers' organizations, extension officers and research teams, a four-week comprehensive online training on farmer field schools (FFS) was provided for all team members. The training was given by farmer field school expert Lilian Beck and was organized in 12 different modules, covering all aspects and steps regarding the farmer field school approach.

A total of 25 project members attended the sessions and training certificates were attributed to those who attended at least 80% of the sessions. These events were made possible through **an additional external funding** acquired by Lilian Beck and SustainSahel. This training was not foreseen in the original proposal but the opportunity to collaborate with an FFS expert Lilian Beck was aptly utilized and benefitted the consortium partners greatly. The team members expressed satisfaction with the possibility of being trained by an expert in the field.

Challenges

The implementation of the local dissemination action plan faced some challenges, which can be summarized as follows:

- The SustainSahel project takes the **security issues** facing most of the Sahelian region very seriously. The insecurity facing some Sahelian countries has increased in recent years, and within two years since the beginning of the project, the situation in the neighboring regions of Koulikoro and Yilou has deserved special attention. SustainSahel is closely observing the development and adjusting the approach where necessary, counting on the careful risk assessment made by the local teams. For example, the location of the last dissemination event in the Sikasso site has been relocated to the town of Sikasso, instead of the village of Zoumana Diassa, due to increased uncertainty in the rural areas just north of the village. The project will continue to carefully monitor the situation, while reasserting the commitment to continuing to contribute to improving the livelihoods of the local rural communities in a context where few interventions still take place.
- The implementation of the local open field day events in Niakhar, Senegal, faced some challenges in the mobilization of the lead farmers in 2022 (see table 1). One of the issues was that the lead farmers were solely appointed by the village traditional leaders, who selected generally the most educated villagers, many of them school teachers. Because the school calendar was not compatible with the open field day events' agenda, the mobilization of the initially selected lead farmers was very poor. A new mission with different project members took place in January 2023 to co-select other lead farmers in the site of Niakhar, in collaboration with the traditional leaders, where the project's objectives were made clearer. The last dissemination event in Niakhar (27th April 2023) counted with a much higher attendance, thanks to this adjustment.
- The accessibility of some parts of the intervention areas can be very challenging, especially in the second event of each year, which coincides with the end of the rainy season. Some villages in the target regions become inaccessible after heavy rains, making it difficult to access them or for the

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lead farmers in remote areas to come to the open field day events. In case of getting stuck in mud, vehicles can face many hours of waiting before being towed away by the nearest help available (see figure 23 in the appendix).

Despite the challenges faced in the implementation of the local dissemination, the local teams managed to organize all of the proposed open field day events so far, showing commitment and dedication to the purpose of these activities.

Looking back and ahead

The first three open field day events in each site were enriching for both farmers and project partners, resulting in a co-learning process that embodies the intended transdisciplinary approach of the project. During the events, researchers, farmers engaged in the development of the demonstration plots and students were invited to share the results and experiences they obtained within the project's process. This consisted particularly in theoretical inputs by experts and students about their results, but also visits to the fields and collective assessment of the treatments' effects on crops, as well as demonstrative activities such as, for example, showing the proper manner of cutting bushes and using the cuttings as mulch. The inputs and the visits were always followed by a meal and interaction between all actors, where farmers could make comments, ask questions and debate about what they have learned and seen.

It was very interesting to note that farmers in different sites have different degrees of knowledge regarding the type of approach promoted by SustainSahel. For example, farmers in Yilou seem to have a higher degree of knowledge regarding techniques such as mulching, assisted natural regeneration, living fences, and other agroforestry and soil regeneration practices, when compared to farmers in the other sites. To farmers in Niakhar and Ouarkhokh, for example, the use of mulch with cuttings from native bushes seemed to be a novel approach, even surprising for most farmers. Similarly, farmers in Koulikoro and Sikasso were surprised to know that some farmers in Burkina Faso didn't burn the spontaneous native bushes in their fields before the rainy season and instead used cuttings as mulch to improve fertility and water retention. The reason for these differences is still unknown, but could be related to different factors, which the project will try to assess in a deeper way during the remaining time of the research process and sharing of experiences.

Learning about the state of knowledge of agroforestry-related approaches in the different sites is essential in order to adapt the content of the open field days to the local reality. For instance, what is new for farmers in Niakhar could perhaps sound uninteresting for some farmers in Yilou, whom might benefit more from more in depth messages about the practices and the underlying concepts, or the new results related with the ongoing livestock-tree/shrub interactions from WVP6, for example. These insights were therefore useful to design better adapted agendas for each site in the third open field day of each site.

For a better insight of farmers experiences during the open field days, see the images in the document's appendix.

2.2 What's new?

SustainSahel's local dissemination approach was discussed and reassessed during the annual meeting of 2023, and some decisions were taken in order to adapt the strategy to the perceived needs and efficiency of the approach.

The two phases of the dissemination approach

So far, the open field days consisted on inviting lead farmers and, in some cases, other actors such as IP members, extension officers and other local farmers, into a single place where the event was held. While these centralized events have been very useful logistically and in order to provide a harmonized introduction to the set of disseminated practices in each site, they would also risk becoming repetitive if the same approach persisted until the end of the project. It was agreed that the local dissemination action plan could be seen in two phases:

- **Phase 1 – Dissemination and training of lead farmers as trainers (2022/2023)**
Lead farmers, project members and other actors come together in each site to share results from the project's research process and experiences. During this phase, lead farmers visit demonstration plots and discuss the different innovations and treatments, which they are invited to test in their own fields, according to their interests. This phase can be seen as the training of lead farmers as future trainers, as they become familiar with the concepts and the methods related to the disseminated practices. Each lead farmer should be visited at least twice by local extension officers engaged with the farmers' organizations during the rainy season. The local extension officers can thus fill up any knowledge gaps regarding the implementation of the practices and help guide its testing in the farmers' fields. It is important to mention that this process happens in parallel with the Innovation Platform process, with a mutual enrichment in terms of insights and co-learning.
- **Phase 2 – Decentralization of the dissemination approach (2024/2025)**
Lead farmers have participated in a minimum of two and a maximum of four (five in the case of Koulikoro) open field days and have been visited on average 4 times by the local extension officer. The lead farmers should now have acquired the knowledge and experience necessary to organize small open field day events in their own fields, inviting neighbouring farmers and in the presence of the local extension officer. This step, to start in the rainy season of 2024, will consolidate the cascading effect of the project's dissemination approach and enable the information to flow to new villages and areas.

The shift in the project's dissemination approach can be visualized in the figures below, with the example of the Koulikoro area.

Figure 1 and 2. The shift of the project’s dissemination approach from a centralized open field day approach to a decentralized one, with lead farmers becoming trainers of other farmers.

Assessing the learning experience and potential adoption of innovations by lead farmers

While WP3 is studying the adoption of the disseminated practices in two project sites (Niakhar and Koulikoro) in depth, and WP2 produced an empirical model of constraints to the adoption of crop-shrub-livestock practices, the process of potential adoption (or non-adoption) of the disseminated practices by the lead farmers had not yet been accounted for in the research process. To fill in this gap, a collaborative effort between WP8, WP2 and WP3 is taking place, producing new socio-economic questionnaires for lead farmers, which will help understand the dynamic of adoption of the practices in an endline survey by the end of the project. These questionnaires are integrated in the follow-up of the lead farmers during the rainy season, which, as previously mentioned, will consist on two visits to each lead farmer by a local extension officer.

This unforeseen collaborative effort will enable to learn more deeply about the impact of the ongoing dissemination approach on the promotion of the disseminated practices and related knowledge flow.

Co-creation of learning materials for farmers

One important aspect of the project's dissemination approach is the production of learning materials that are adequate for the farmers in the context of the project's sites and improved by farmers' themselves in an iterative way.

SustainSahel's intervention areas face challenges such as widespread illiteracy, lack of access to adequate information sources, exclusion of women and youth from access to information and insufficient or inexistent agricultural extension services. In this context, the project is experimenting with the use of learning materials that can contribute to increased access to relevant information for farmers concerning CSL practices. The perspectives of farmers are taken into account in the design of those materials. Furthermore, the lead farmers will help assess their quality in conveying relevant information, enabling their improvement and potential adjustments in new versions that can be used for farmers beyond the intervention areas. Examples of used innovative learning materials are:

- Distribution of mini-SD memory cards loaded with CSL related videos in the local languages:
All lead farmers received a mini-SD memory card with nine videos portraying CSL related videos translated into the local languages of each site. The decision to use the video on mobile-phone approach is related to the fact that all lead farmers either have a mobile phone compatible with the use of mini-SD memory cards or have at least one family member who has it. Farmers in the intervention areas have the habit of watching videos on their mobile phones for entertainment or learning, which makes this learning tool well adapted to the local context. The nine videos were collaboratively selected with Access Agriculture from their large online video database, considering their relevance regarding the use of CSL practices. The videos had to be dubbed into the local languages of the six project sites, in case those versions didn't exist already. The mini-SD cards were shared with farmers in the second open field day events of 2022 (see figure 13 in the appendix), and by the beginning of 2023 in case of Sikasso. A short questionnaire to address farmers' perceptions and preferences regarding the shared videos will generate insights for future dissemination activities.
- A visual brochure that unfolds into a wall poster portraying an agroforestry system adapted to the local context:
A visual brochure showing the benefits of trees and shrubs for the local agricultural systems is in the last phase of production and the first edition should be printed in July 2023. The brochure has little text and relies on pictures and illustrations to convey the main messages. It also includes a list of relevant species to be included in the fields and the respective benefits. The amount of text in the brochure was the subject of debate, due to the widespread illiteracy in the rural areas. However, it was decided that small amounts of text are not problematic because every household has at least one member that is literate. The illustrated example of a suitable agroforestry system for the Sahel was collaboratively designed by the production team and the project's experts. This first version will be a test version to be assessed by lead farmers. Their feedback will enable adjusting the illustration so that the depicted system can reflect the needs and envisioning of the farmers. The two-fold use of this learning material, as a brochure or a wall poster,

makes its use by farmers more flexible, since they can read the brochure and pass it on to others, and/or use it as a wall poster, something that is quite appreciated by local farmers. The illustrations are originals, produced by SustainSahel. The first version of the co-designed agroforestry system can be seen in figure 3.

Figure 3. Illustrated example of an agroforestry system adapted to the Sahel, included in the foldable brochure. This illustration can be used as a wall poster by farmers.

- New project videos:

In collaboration with Access Agriculture, SustainSahel will produce a minimum of 4 and a maximum of 5 new project videos showcasing the results and insights generated by the project. The video production process is set to begin in the second half of 2023, with the first interviews and field visits taking place. The release of these videos is expected for 2025.

Additionally, a new video will be produced from the rich illustration produced by the project, showing a detailed proposal of an agroforestry system adapted to the Sahel. The release of this video is scheduled for August 2023.

- Audio agroecological training:

External funding provided an opportunity to perform a FiBL led pilot test of an audio agroecological training in Sikasso, one of SustainSahel's sites in Mali. The local implementation partner of the pilot test is the project partner AOPP, the national farmers' organization. A new partnership with a national telecommunication company enabled the adaptation of the written agroecological training to voice messages, adapting the content to the local reality and to the specific messages of SustainSahel. The next step was the involvement of around 400 farmers in the test through AOPP. The farmers were first approached with a phone call and they simply had to follow the audio instructions and the

phone keys to progress to the next voice messages and respond to quizzes. Preliminary data shows that the engagement of farmers in the training was around 80%, which was considered high for this kind of approach by the telecommunication partner. An endline survey with the involved farmers will enable to better understand the impact of this type of training on farmers' perceptions and behavioural change.

Besides the learning materials produced by the project, promotional materials such as T-shirts, caps and bags has been produced and distributed to all lead farmers. Also, the use of the produced illustrations for other purposes is also under discussion, for example for field signs to be placed in the intervention areas.

3. Bridges with other WPs and projects

3.1 SustainSahel's internal sharing forum

The project review report released in June 2022 had as its first recommendation the creation of "a dedicated internal mechanism in which collaboration at the content level is regularly facilitated". According to the review report, the creation of such mechanism would "create synergies and strengthen interdisciplinary and, when linked to the IPs, transdisciplinary elements in the project". This recommendation is aligned with the team's perspective that communication and information flow between WPs and national teams could be improved, benefiting the project as a whole and contributing to reaching its goals and ambitions.

Following internal deliberation, the creation of a sharing forum was approved in the project's General Assembly during the annual meeting in Ouagadougou, February 2023. It was collectively decided that the project's internal sharing forum would be composed of representatives of each partner institution, in addition to the coordinators of WP2 and WP8, who will jointly stir the mechanism.

The institutions' representatives' role is to actively seek updates on the project's research and implementation process from their teams, collecting the key messages and insights of those processes while systematizing the related content. The representatives will then meet and share the findings, providing a consolidated report for the whole project team.

One of the key roles of this new internal sharing mechanism is to provide relevant information for the open field days and even more importantly, the IP discussions. This can reinforce the flow of key information across countries and widen the scope of the IP discussions.

The first internal sharing forum was held in June 2023 and the next meeting is scheduled for September 2023, in time to provide a consolidated report before the next round of IP discussions in most sites. The consolidated report is expected to contribute to enriching not only the IP discussions, but also the open field days agendas and discussions, as well as the projects' communication tools such as the newsletter, social media, and others.

3.2 Interactions with other projects

DAAPS: Expanding SustainSahel’s outreach

As mentioned in deliverable 8.1, an additional external funding provided a unique opportunity to expand SustainSahel’s dissemination approach and integrate three new partners in the process: Agrisud in Senegal, AMSD in Mali and Tiipaalga in Burkina Faso. The three NGOs widen the range of actors in the project’s sphere and introduce a dynamic approach to the dissemination approach, constituting the so-called DAAPS project.

The FiBL coordinated “Disseminating Appropriate Agroforestry Practices in the Sahel” (DAAPS) is in practice an extension of SustainSahel’s open field days efforts and the three NGOs work in close collaboration with the project partners. The DAAPS sister project thus enables SustainSahel to reach a higher number of farmers and a wider geographical scope as initially previewed.

The DAAPS project lasts from January 2022 to December 2023 and adds 12 extra open field days to SustainSahel’s list. Each NGO is responsible for organizing two open field days per year in collaboration with SustainSahel partners, including the key messages of the project in the agenda.

The open field days organized by DAAPS take place in three of SustainSahel’s sites – Niakhar, Koulikoro and Yilou. In Koulikoro, the events take place in a different area than those of SustainSahel, and in Niakhar and Yilou, the events take place in the same areas, in complementarity and close collaboration with the local SustainSahel partners, who participate in the events as well. In the case of Niakhar, WP3’s team is well informed about the events so that there is no interference with the ongoing adoption study. The dates and number of participants in the DAAPS’s open field days can be seen in table 2.

Table 2. Dates and total number of participants in the open field days organized by the DAAPS partners.

Country/NGO	Event date	Total participants
Senegal - Agrisud	08/06/2022	224
	16/11/2022	210
	09/05/2023	117
Mali - AMSD	02/07/2022	126
	20/10/2022	258
	27/05/2023	162
Burkina Faso - Tiipaalga	20/06/2022	255
	29/11/2022	106
	22/06/2023	93

Besides the organization of a total of 12 open field days, the DAAPS project also implements tree nurseries in several villages in the above-mentioned areas, which produce local tree and bush seedlings to be distributed to farmers. Additionally, the three NGOs organize video screenings in villages with videos that have been co-selected with SustainSahel’s team. For a visual insight concerning the activities of the DAAPS, see figures 16-22 in the document’s appendix.

Collaboration with other H2020 and EU-DESIRA projects

The SustainSahel project is in close contact with the [FairSahel](#) project, with which concrete bridges have already been forged. The two projects are collaborating closely in two of the project's sites, with an exchange of information between the projects' teams and synergies in the organization of the innovation platforms of Sikasso and Koussanar. Besides, the two projects are co-hosting an info point at the DG INTPA European Commission on the 5th of September 2023, which will further deepen the collaboration.

Contacts have also been established with the SustinAfrica project, and a collaboration between the projects in the dissemination and information exchange elements is under consideration. Similarly, the project has established contacts with the [EWA-BELT](#), [CaSSECS](#), and RAMSES projects, with a similar geographical scope.

4. Appendix – Images of SustainSahel’s open field days

Figure 4. Family photo of the first open field day in the site of Saria, Burkina Faso (31/05/2022).

Figure 5. Lead farmers and other stakeholders are introduced to the project’s dissemination approach and goals in the first open field day in Koulikoro, Mali (11/06/2022).

Figure 6. Farmers visit the fields in Ouarkhokh, Senegal, in their first contact with one of the project's trials (23/06/2022).

Figure 7. Lead farmers visit one of the demonstration plots in Saria, Burkina Faso, where a local farmer explains the different treatments using mulch from native bushes and the perceived effects on crops (26/09/2022).

Figure 8. Visual assessment of the effects of different mulch and compost types using native trees and bushes on sorghum, at the on-station research trial at Saria's INERA station, during the second open field day in the site (26/09/2022).

Figure 9. Lead farmers visit the on-station trial at Katibougou in Koulikoro, Mali, led by IPR (19/10/2022).

Figure 10. Farmers collect cuttings of *Gliricida sepium* at the Katibougou research station (19/10/2022 - Koulikoro, Mali). *Gliricidia* is a multi-purpose bush that can be integrated in the local agroforestry systems and can be used as good quality mulch and forage for livestock.

Figure 11. Farmers and other participants visit a field trial in Mafeya (Koulikoro site, Mali), during an open field day (24/10/2022).

Figure 12. Family photo during the field visit of the second open field day in Yilou, Burkina Faso (03/11/2022).

Figure 13. Farmers show each other the agroforestry related videos shared by SustainSahel via mini-SD memory cards, during the second open field day in Ouarkhokh (21/09/2022).

Figure 14. Showing drone images of experimental fields to the participants of the second open field day in Ouarkhokh (21/09/2022). The drone pictures provided new perspectives of the fields and of how the vegetative growth of crops was affected by the different treatments and the proximity of bushes and trees, enriching the discussions among participants.

Figure 15. Distribution of hundreds of tree and bush seedlings to farmers in Ouarkhokh, Senegal, during the second open field day (21/09/2022).

Figure 16. Demonstration of a compost production technique during the open field day organized by the AMSD NGO in the region of Koulikoro, Mali (20/10/2022). The event counted with the active participation of SustainSahel's partners who found the demonstrative approach interesting and later applied it in other dissemination events.

Figure 17. Farmers visit the nursery and forage bank implemented by AMSD in collaboration with SustainSahel (Koulikoro, Mali – 20/10/2022).

Figures 18 and 19. Exhibition displaying local agroforestry derived products at the open field day organized by Tiipaalga in Yilou, Burkina Faso, within the frame of the DAAPS (20/06/2022).

Figures 20 and 21. Collective tree planting action in the farmers' fields organized by Agrisud in the region of Niakhar, Senegal, in collaboration with SustainSahel (16/11/2022).

Figure 22. Tree and bush nursery implemented by the NGO Tiipaalga in the site of Yilou, in collaboration with SustainSahel.

Figure 23. Inaccessible roads and cars getting stuck on mud are a common challenge for the field missions during the rainy seasons. In this picture, one part of the project's team got stuck for a few hours before the second open field day in Niakhar, Senegal (23/09/2022).